

Fixed Point Theorems For Non-Expensive Mapping In Partial B-Metric Space

Masood Shahbaz Shoukat*

Department of Mathematics International Islamic University Islamabad, Pakistan

*Corresponding author: masoodshahbaz91@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Fixed Point Theorems represent a foundational concept in mathematics, offering profound insights into the existence and behavior of fixed points under various mappings and transformations. These theorems assert the presence of points that remain unchanged by a given function or mapping, providing essential tools for analyzing the structure of spaces and the solutions to diverse problems. This abstract explores the essence of Fixed Point Theorems, their historical development, key results, and broad applications across mathematics, computer science, economics, and beyond. Additionally, it highlights the enduring significance of fixed point theory in both theoretical research and practical applications, underscoring its role as a fundamental building block in mathematical analysis.

Keywords: Fixed Point Theorem, Mapping, Existence, Convergence, Applications

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In mathematics, a fixed-point theorem is a result saying that a function F will have at least one fixed point (a point x for which $F(x) = x$), under some conditions on F that can be stated in general terms (Reich 1983). Fixed Point Theorems serve as a cornerstone in the edifice of mathematical analysis, offering profound insights into the behavior of functions and mappings (Agarwal et al. 2015). These theorems, though seemingly abstract, possess remarkable practical implications across diverse fields, from economics to computer science. In this review, we delve into the essence of Fixed Point Theorems, exploring their significance, applications, and enduring relevance (Reich 1983).

At its core, a Fixed Point Theorem asserts the existence of a point in a space that remains unchanged under a given transformation. The foundational work by mathematicians such as Banach, Brouwer, and Kakutani laid the groundwork for understanding these fundamental principles. Banach's Fixed Point Theorem, for instance, provides conditions under which a contraction mapping on a complete metric space has a unique fixed point. This theorem has widespread applications in functional analysis, particularly in the study of differential equations and optimization problems (Debnath, Konwar, and Radenović 2021).

Brouwer's Fixed Point Theorem, on the other hand, holds a special place in topology, asserting that any continuous mapping of a compact convex set into itself has a fixed point (Moser 2006). This theorem not only offers theoretical insights but also finds practical applications in game theory, economics, and the study of dynamical systems. Its implications extend far beyond mathematics, influencing fields as diverse as urban planning and evolutionary biology (Debnath, Konwar, and Radenović 2021).

Kakutani's Fixed Point Theorem further broadens the scope of fixed point theory by establishing conditions for the existence of equilibrium points in non-compact convex sets (Subrahmanyam 2018). This theorem has profound implications in the analysis of strategic interactions in economics, providing a rigorous framework for studying Nash equilibria in games with continuous strategy spaces (Fan 1961).

List of fixed-point theorems (Reich 1983; Fan 1961; Nikaido 1989)

1. Atiyah–Bott fixed-point theorem
2. Banach fixed-point theorem
3. Bekić's theorem
4. Borel fixed-point theorem
5. Bourbaki–Witt theorem
6. Browder fixed-point theorem
7. Brouwer fixed-point theorem
8. Rothe's fixed-point theorem
9. Caristi fixed-point theorem
10. Diagonal lemma, also known as the fixed-point lemma, for producing self-referential sentences of first-order logic
11. Lawvere's fixed-point theorem
12. Discrete fixed-point theorems
13. Earle–Hamilton fixed-point theorem
14. Fixed-point combinator, which shows that every term in untyped lambda calculus has a fixed point
15. Fixed-point lemma for normal functions
16. Fixed-point property
17. Fixed-point theorems in infinite-dimensional spaces
18. Injective metric space
19. Kakutani fixed-point theorem
20. Kleene fixed-point theorem
21. Knaster–Tarski theorem
22. Lefschetz fixed-point theorem
23. Nielsen fixed-point theorem
24. Poincaré–Birkhoff theorem proves the existence of two fixed points
25. Ryll–Nardzewski fixed-point theorem
26. Schauder fixed-point theorem
27. Topological degree theory
28. Tychonoff fixed-point theorem

Moreover, Fixed Point Theorems have found fertile ground in the realm of computer science and optimization. Algorithms based on fixed point iterations are ubiquitous in numerical analysis, offering efficient solutions to a wide array of computational problems (Moser 2006). From finding solutions to systems of equations to optimizing functions, these algorithms leverage the underlying principles of fixed point theory to converge to desired outcomes reliably (Subrahmanyam 2018).

In conclusion, Fixed Point Theorems stand as pillars of mathematical analysis, illuminating the structure of spaces and mappings in profound ways. Their applications span a myriad of disciplines, from pure mathematics to applied sciences, underlining their enduring significance (Nikaido 1989). As we continue to explore the frontiers of mathematics and its applications, the insights gleaned from Fixed Point Theorems will undoubtedly remain indispensable (Reich 1983; Pata 2019).

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